

Why a better modal theory of biological function is needed

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WHATIF
WASWÄREWENN

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- 1 Etiological analysis (Wright 1973, Millikan 1989, Neander 1991)
- 2 Systemic analysis (Cummins 1976, Craver 2001)
- 3 Propensity analysis (Bigelow & Pargetter 1987)
- 4 Goal-oriented analysis (McLaughlin 2001, Mossio et al. 2009)
- 5 Biostatistical analysis (Boorse 1975, Garson & Piccinini 2013)

A challenger appears! **Modal analysis (Nanay 2010)**

The modal theory

Argument for the modal analysis (adapted from Nany 2010)

P1 1.-5. require a criterion of trait-type individuation

P2 No criterion of trait-type individuation is tenable

P3 Modal analysis doesn't require a criterion of trait-type individuation

C1 1.-5. are not tenable

C2 Modal analysis is to be preferred over 1.-5.

Assumption

- P1 is true (but see Neander and Rosenberg 2013)
- P2 is true (but see Kiritani 2011)

Claim

- P3 is false
- Even if P3 is true, C2 does not follow

1 Spelling out the modal theory

2 Arguing for my claim

- Vacuous truth proliferates functions (vs C2)
- Centering assimilates 'function' to 'use' (vs C2)
- Malfunction entails trait-type dependence (vs P3)

3 Conclusion

How to spell out the modal theory?

Modal theory (adapted from Nanay 2010, 421)

Performing F is a function of organism O 's token trait x at time t iff if x were F -ing at t , x 's F -ing at t would contribute to O 's inclusive fitness.

- How to spell out the counterfactual conditional?
- “Any theory of counterfactuals could be used” (Nanay 2010, 421).
- For simplicity, Nanay uses Lewis' (1973) theory.

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Syntax

$$\phi \quad := \quad p \in P \mid \neg\phi \mid \phi \wedge \psi \mid \phi \vee \psi \mid \phi \rightarrow \psi \mid \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$$

Models

A model is a triple $\mathcal{M} = \langle W, <, V \rangle$ where:

- W is a non-empty set interpreted as the set of possible worlds,
- $<$ is a strict partial order on $W_\alpha \subseteq W$ interpreted as the comparative similarity or closeness relation with respect to the actual world $\alpha \in W$ where W_α is interpreted as the set of possible worlds which are accessible from α ,
- V is a function which assigns a truth-value to every atomic sentence $p \in P$ at every possible world $w \in W$ yielding the set of possible worlds $V(p) \subseteq W$ at which p is true.

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Notation

$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$:= ϕ is true at the possible world $w \in W$ in model \mathcal{M}

Limit Assumption (adapted from Lewis 1973, 19f.)

\mathcal{M} is limited iff $<$ is well-founded

Closest possible ϕ -worlds $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} \subseteq W_\alpha$ in \mathcal{M}

$w \in C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}}$ iff $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$ and $\neg \exists w' \in W_\alpha$ such that $w' < w$

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Truth-conditions

$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash p$	iff	$w \in V(p)$
$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \neg\phi$	iff	not $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$
$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi \vee \psi$	iff	$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$ or $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$
$\mathcal{M}, \alpha \vDash \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$	iff	$\forall w \in C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} : \mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$

Relatively close worlds $R^{\mathcal{M}} \subseteq W_\alpha$ in \mathcal{M} (compare Nanay 2010, 422)

$w \in R^{\mathcal{M}}$ iff $w \in W_\alpha$ and w is close enough to α given E

Truth-conditions, revised

$\mathcal{M}, \alpha \vDash \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$ iff $\forall w \in C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}} : \mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$

The modal theory spelled out

Notation

χ := organism O 's token trait x is doing F at t

ξ := x 's doing F at t contributes to O 's inclusive fitness

Modal theory

$\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models$ performing F is function of x at t iff $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \chi \rightsquigarrow \xi$

Vacuous truth proliferates functions

Vacuous truth (compare Lewis 1973, 16)

$\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$ is vacuously true iff $C_\phi \cap R = \emptyset$

Vacuous truth proliferates functions

Notation

- χ := organism O 's token trait x is doing F at t
 ξ := x 's doing F at t contributes to O 's inclusive fitness

Proliferation schema

- P1 Let F be something biologically impossible
C1 By P1, $\neg \exists w \in W_\alpha$ such that $\mathcal{M}, w \models \chi$
C2 By C1, $C_\chi^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$ and hence $C_\chi^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$
C3 By C2 and vacuous truth, $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \chi \rightsquigarrow \xi$
C4 By C3 and the modal analysis, performing F is a function of x

Example

Obama's heart has the function to pump acid, to digest food, to make Obama immortal, to prevent nuclear wars...

Centering assimilates 'function' to 'use'

Centering (adapted from Lewis 1973, 14f.)

\mathcal{M} is centered iff $\neg \exists w \in W_\alpha$ such that $w < \alpha$

- For any centered model \mathcal{M} , if $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \phi$, then $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}} = \{\alpha\}$
- So $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$ only if $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \psi$

Centering assimilates ‘function’ to ‘use’

It would indeed be a worrying consequence of my view if it ended up assimilating function to use [...]. But this is not the case. What a trait is being used for is determined by what goes on in the actual world. Function (and, arguably, usefulness), in contrast, depends on what goes on in nearby possible worlds. Function is a modal concept; use is not. (Nanay 2010, 427)

Centering assimilates 'function' to 'use'

Notation

- χ := organism O 's token trait x is doing F at t
 ξ := x 's doing F at t contributes to O 's inclusive fitness

Assimilation schema

- P1 $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \chi$
C1 By P1 & centering, $C_x^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}} = \{\alpha\}$
C2 By C1, $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \chi \rightsquigarrow \xi$ only if $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \xi$
C3 By C2 & modal theory, performing F is a function of x at t only if $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \xi$, i.e. depends on what goes on in the actual world

Exceptions

- x malfunctions at t
- x 's doing F at t is a disposition

Malfunction entails trait-type dependence

Notation

χ := organism O 's token trait x is doing F at t

ξ := x 's doing F at t contributes to O 's inclusive fitness

Malfunction

x malfunctions at t at α with respect to F iff

- $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \neg\chi$, and
- $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \chi \rightsquigarrow \xi$

Malfunction entails trait-type dependence

Counterparts

O_C := O 's counterpart living at w

x_C := O_C 's trait doing F at t

- Assume that x malfunctions at α at t with respect to F .
- By malfunction, x has the function to perform F thanks to the fact that x_C is F -ing at t and that x_C 's F -ing contributes to O_C 's inclusive fitness.
- So of x and x_C are not of the same trait-type, the function of x to perform F is random.

Example

Obama's actually malfunctioning heart (God forbid) has the function to pump blood due to Obama's counterparts heart (and not leg, brain or liver) pumping blood and this contributing to the counterpart's inclusive fitness.

Argument for the modal analysis (adapted from Nany 2010)

- P1 All analyses of function require a criterion of trait-type individuation
- P2 No criterion of trait-type individuation is tenable
- P3 Modal analysis doesn't require a criterion of trait-type individuation**
- C1 All other analyses of function are not tenable
- C2 Modal analysis is to be preferred over all other analyses of function**

Objections

- Modal analysis proliferates functions (vs C2)
- Modal analysis assimilates 'function' to 'use' (vs C2)
- Modal analysis trait-type dependent in cases of malfunction (vs P3)

THANK YOU!

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